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Implication of Feedback and Praise on Mindset

Chandan Suman

Department of Foreign Language, Faculty of Arts, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi

Abstract

This research paper examines the impact of feedback and praises on mindset development, focusing on fixed and growth mindsets. It discusses the importance of providing specific, timely, and constructive feedback to enhance mindset development. It also discusses the influence of praises on mindset beliefs and motivation, emphasizing the importance of praising efforts, strategies, and progress rather than focusing solely on innate abilities. The paper discusses potential challenges and limitations of providing effective feedback and praises, and offers practical recommendations for educators, parents, and policymakers to promote a culture of continuous improvement, meaningful feedback, and cultivating a growth-oriented mindset in educational settings.

Keywords: Feedback, Praises, Growth Mindset, Fixed Mindset, Intelligence, Learning Strategies, Achievement, Constructive Criticism

1. Introduction

Feedback and praise have long been acknowledged as essential components of the learning process in educational environments. They are effective instruments for giving individuals with direction, encouragement, and motivation. Recent study, however, has investigated about the enormous impact that feedback and praises can have on people's mindsets and ideas about their intelligence, abilities, and potential for advancement (Ashford & De Stobbeleir, 2013; Carless & Boud, 2018; Winstone et al., 2019; Zher Huey & Hussain, 2010).

The purpose of this study paper is to investigate the effects of feedback and praise on mindset, with a particular emphasis on how they can influence individuals' beliefs and attitudes concerning their own capabilities. The purpose of this research is to provide a comprehensive overview of the existing literature by investigating the impact of various types of feedback and praises on mindset formation, motivation, and achievement.

To begin, it is essential to consider the concept of mindset. Individuals' beliefs about the nature of intelligence and talent are referred to as their mindset. Carol Dweck, a Stanford psychologist, proposed the distinction between fixed and growth mindsets. Those who hold a fixed mindset feel that intelligence and abilities are fixed attributes, whereas those who hold a growth mindset believe that they can be developed via hard work, successful strategies, and perseverance (Barbouta et al., 2020; C. S. Dweck, 2017; Manchi Chao et al., 2017; Rohne, 2015; Sanguras, 2021).

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The impact of feedback on attitude formation is a major emphasis of this research. According to research, feedback that emphasises effort, progress, and the application of effective learning tools can create a growth mindset (Carless et al., 2011; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996; Krenn et al., 2013; Seethamraju & Shaw, 2015). Feedback that focuses entirely on natural abilities and outcomes, on the other hand, might perpetuate a fixed attitude and undermine individuals' willingness to learn and improve (Earley et al., 1990; Mcleod et al., 1992; Podsakoff & Farh, 1989). Similarly, praises have an important role in mindset formation. Individuals' ideas about their abilities and potential might be shaped by the type of praise they receive. Person praise that emphasises individual's internal qualities and talent has the potential to reinforce a fixed mindset. Process praise, on the other hand, which recognises individuals' efforts, strategies, and growth, can create a growth mindset and motivate people to embrace challenges and persevere in the face of difficulty.

It is crucial to acknowledge that providing appropriate feedback and praise can be complex and difficult. It necessitates careful consideration of the needs and goals of individuals, as well as the precise context in which feedback and praise are offered. Furthermore, providing a supportive and growth-oriented learning environment is critical for cultivating a positive mindset and promoting continuous improvement (Glerum et al., 2019, 2020; Pomerantz & Kempner, 2013).

Educators, parents, and policymakers can use feedback and praise to establish optimal learning environments that encourage a growth mindset, intrinsic motivation, and a love of learning by understanding the implications of feedback and praise on Mindset (Calingasan & Plata, 2022; Kamins & Dweck, 1999; Mueller & Dweck, 1998). This study paper will present insights and practical recommendations to assist stakeholders in harnessing the power of feedback and praise to build a mindset that fosters resilience, effort, and a belief in one's own ability to grow and achieve.

Overall, investigating feedback and praises in relation to mindset is critical for understanding how these elements might change people's beliefs, attitudes, and motivations. This study intends to contribute to ongoing efforts to create positive attitudes and improve learning experiences by investigating the implications of feedback and praise on mindset.

2. Concept of mindset: Fixed mindset and growth mindset

The fixed mindset is characterised by the belief that one's talents and abilities are predetermined, leading people to seek validation and avoid challenges that may call their perceived abilities into question. The growth mindset, on the other hand, perceives challenges as chances for growth, rewards effort and resilience, and considers failures as learning opportunities rather than indicators of inherent limitations (C. S. Dweck, 2017).

The effects of mindset on many dimensions of people's lives, such as academic achievement, personal relationships, and overall well-being, are significant. According to research, people

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with a growth mindset are more likely to face obstacles with a positive attitude, to be more resilient, and to use effective learning practises. They are also more inclined to endure in the face of setbacks and to see failure as a necessary step to success (Manchi Chao et al., 2017; Nalipay et al., 2021; Sanguras, 2021). Individuals with a fixed mindset, on the other hand, prefer to avoid difficulties, worry failure, and may experience a reduction in motivation and performance over time (C. Dweck, 2019; Wormeli, 2018).

People with Fixed Mindset believes that intellect and talent are permanent, refuses challenges in order to avoid failure, ignores feedback from others, and feels concerned by others' success. This mindset masks weaknesses in order to avoid being judged by others, takes criticism personally, quits up easily, and sees effort as a sign of weakness. Furthermore, success is more likely to be attributed to external variables such as luck or talent, whereas failure is more likely to be attributed to internal factors such as a lack of intelligence or ability.

Person with a growth mindset believes that intelligence and talent can be grown by hard work, which is why they seek out challenges, learn from their failures, and appreciate feedback from others, and are most significantly inspired by others' success. They are honest about their weaknesses and limitations, view criticism as an opportunity to grow, and constantly persevere in the face of difficulty. They regard effort as a show of strength, and they are more inclined to credit success to internal variables such as hard work and dedication, while losing on external reasons such as a lack of opportunity or resources.

3. Role of feedback in mindset development

Two forms of feedback are particularly relevant in the context of mindset development: process-focused feedback and person-focused feedback. Process-focused feedback stresses effort, strategies, and areas for growth, emphasising the malleability of abilities and the significance of continual learning (Chen et al., 2020; Yeager & Dweck, 2012). Person-focused feedback, on the other hand, focuses on innate qualities or fixed attributes, which may reinforce a fixed mindset and discourage further growth (Tang et al., 2019; Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

According to research, feedback that emphasises effort, progress, and specific strategies encourages a growth mindset by instilling confidence in one's ability to improve and learn (Aulia et al., 2022; Ebenezer Nrumah et al., 2021; Kosterlitz, 2015). Feedback that focuses only on natural abilities or personal characteristics, on the other hand, may contribute to the creation or reinforcement of a fixed mindset, in which people believe their abilities are permanent and unchangeable (Bostwick et al., 2020; Yip, 2018).

Educators and individuals in various settings all play an important role in cultivating a growth mindset through providing feedback. They can implement specific strategies and best practice for providing effective feedback that fosters a growth mindset, such as providing specific and actionable feedback, praising effort and progress, focusing on the learning process, and

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cultivating a supportive and constructive feedback culture (Adcroft, 2010; Bailey & Garner, 2010; Park & Shon, 2020).

Feedback can assist people in recognising their own strengths and limitations. People that receive feedback might learn what they are doing well and where they need to improve. This can assist them in developing a more accurate view of their capabilities and setting realistic goals for themselves. People who receive feedback are more likely to have a growth mentality and are more inclined to feel that their abilities can be developed with hard work and dedication when they get feedback that focuses on their effort and improvement. This can improve motivation and willingness to take on new challenges. People who get feedback can learn from their mistakes. People who receive feedback on their mistakes might learn from them and avoid repeating them in the future. This can assist them improve their performance and achieve their objectives. It is crucial to recognise, however, that not all feedback is created equal. Feedback must be specific, timely, constructive, and positive in order to be helpful in creating a growth mentality.

Specific: Specific and actionable feedback is preferred. This implies that it should concentrate on certain habits or skills that can be enhanced.

Timely: Feedback should be provided as soon as possible. This means that it should be delivered immediately after the action or skill occurred.

Constructive: The feedback should be constructive and beneficial. This means that instead of simply criticising the person, it should focus on helping them develop.

Positive: Positive and encouraging feedback should be provided. This means that it should emphasise the individual's abilities and potential rather than their faults.

Understanding the role of feedback in mindset development is critical for educators, and education policymakers aiming to establish an effective learning and growth environment (Baghurst et al., 2012; Earley et al., 1990). Individuals can create a resilient attitude, improve their learning experiences, and unlock their full potential for personal and professional progress by harnessing the power of feedback and adopting a growth-oriented feedback approach (Koka & Hein, 2005; Lai, 2011).

4. *Role of Praises in mindset development*

There are two types of praises that are particularly essential in mindset development: person praises and process praises. Person-focused praises emphasise natural traits like intelligence or talent, which can encourage a fixed mindset by implying that abilities are fixed and unchangeable. Process-focused compliments, on the other hand, emphasise effort, strategies, and improvement, encouraging a growth mindset by emphasising the value of learning, perseverance, and development (Glerum et al., 2019, 2020; Mueller & Dweck, 1998).

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Praise can foster a growth mindset, where individuals believe intelligence and abilities can be developed through hard work and effort. However, it can also foster a fixed mindset, where individuals view their intelligence as fixed traits (Calingasan & Plata, 2022; Kamins & Dweck, 1999; Mueller & Dweck, 1998). The type of praise given is crucial, with process praise promoting a growth mindset more than person-praise, which focuses on natural talent (Glerum et al., 2019, 2020; Pomerantz & Kempner, 2013). Proper timing is also crucial, with praise given after failure or mistakes helping individuals learn from their experiences and grow (Glerum et al., 2019; Pomerantz & Kempner, 2013).

Process praise, which emphasizes effort and strategies, is more likely to promote a growth mindset than person praise, which focuses on a person's natural talent or intelligence. For instance, a child praised for working hard on a math problem is more likely to develop a growth mindset, as they see they can improve their skills through hard work. Conversely, a child praised for being smart or talented at math is more likely to develop a fixed mindset, limiting their ability to take on new challenges (Bostwick et al., 2017; Degol et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2021). To promote a growth mindset, focus on effort and strategies, avoid person praise, and praise after failure or mistakes. Overall, praise is a powerful tool for fostering a growth mindset, but it should be used constructively and helpfully.

Praise can help people feel better about themselves and their achievements. People are more likely to feel confident and capable when they are praised. This can improve motivation and willingness to take on new challenges. Praise can aid in the development of a growth mindset. People are more prone to feel that their abilities can be increased via hard work and dedication when they are acknowledged for their effort and improvement. This can improve motivation and willingness to take on new challenges. People who receive praise are more likely to learn from their mistakes. People are more likely to regard mistakes as an opportunity to learn and improve when they are appreciated for their effort, even when they make mistakes. This can result in enhanced tolerance and tendency to take risks.

5. *Feedback that Promotes Growth Mindset in Individuals:*

Specific and Detailed Feedback: Give explicit and detailed feedback, emphasising strengths and areas for improvement. This assists individuals in understanding their progress and identifying particular activities to improve abilities (Zher Huey & Hussain, 2010)

Growth-Oriented Feedback: Organize feedback in a growth-oriented manner, stressing individuals' efforts, approaches, and progress in viewing problems as chances for progress rather than evidence of fixed abilities (Ashford & De Stobbeir, 2013).

Constructive Criticism: Provide constructive feedback with concrete suggestions for development. Avoid using overly judgmental or negative language, and instead offer advice

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on how individuals might improve their talents and overcome hurdles (Carless & Boud, 2018).

Incremental Progress Feedback: Recognize and celebrate tiny successes and incremental progress along the way. This reinforces the notion that growth occurs via consistent effort and improvement (Carless & Boud, 2018).

Process-Oriented Feedback: Rather than focusing exclusively on the outcome, emphasise the individual's effort, perseverance, and effective learning approaches. Emphasize the significance of the learning process and the necessity of skill development on time (Carless et al., 2011).

Encouragement of Challenges: Encourage people to accept challenges and see them as chances to learn and grow. Highlight the importance of failures and mistakes as part of the learning process, as they can lead to useful insights and growth.

Feedback on Goal Setting: Give feedback on individuals' goal-making efforts, assisting them in setting realistic and attainable goals. Provide assistance in breaking down major goals into smaller, more achievable tasks, as well as measuring progress (Krenn et al., 2013).

Feedback on Self-Reflection: Encourage to think about their own learning and progress. Provide feedback that encourages self-evaluation, self-awareness, and self-regulation, allowing individuals to take ownership of their own development (Krenn et al., 2013).

Supportive and Encouraging Language: When giving feedback, use encouraging and helpful language. Encourage to trust in their capabilities, to have faith in their potential for progress, and to emphasise the significance of perseverance and resilience (Khajavy et al., 2021).

Feedback on Effort and Growth Mindset: Recognize and appreciate people's efforts, resilience, and willingness to face challenges. Emphasize the link between effort and growth, highlighting that skills and abilities may be developed via dedication and effort (Abuhassan & Bates, 2015; Rautiainen et al., 2017).

Finally, effective feedback should be personalised to the requirements and preferences of each individual, taking into account their specific goals and learning styles. Individuals can develop a positive attitude toward learning, embrace challenges, and strive for continuous progress through receiving feedback that develops a growth mindset.

6. Praises that Promote Growth Mindset in Individuals:

Effort and Persistence: Individuals should be appreciated for their hard work, resilience, and dedication in their efforts. Recognize their dedication to learning and readiness to put in the effort required to reach their goals (Csizér & Dörnyei, 2005).

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Strategies and Approaches: Individuals' effective strategies, problem-solving abilities, and creative approaches to assignments should be highlighted. Recognize their adaptability, critical thinking, and imagination (Ames & Archer, 1988).

Improvement and Progress: Celebrate people's progress and improvement over time. Recognize the precise areas where they have improved, whether it is learning new abilities, improving knowledge, or developing a deeper understanding (Ames & Archer, 1988b; khellab et al., 2022).

Resilience and Overcoming Challenges: Individuals should be praised for their perseverance in the face of defeat. Recognize their ability to bounce back, learn from mistakes, and persevere in the face of failure (Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

Taking Risks and Stepping Out of Comfort Zones: Individuals who are willing to take risks and go outside of their comfort zones should be praised. Highlight their resilience and readiness to try new things, which promotes personal growth and development.

Self-Reflection and Self-Awareness: Individuals who exhibit self-reflection and self-awareness should be praised. Recognize their abilities to evaluate their own strengths and limitations, seek feedback, and actively engage on self-improvement (Calingasan & Plata, 2022; Kamins & Dweck, 1999).

Collaboration and Teamwork: Individuals should be praised for their collaborative abilities and capacity to work effectively in teams. Recognize their contribution to fostering an inclusive and positive learning environment (Barbouta et al., 2020; Ko, 2023; Nalipay et al., 2021; Sanguras, 2021; Yu & McLellan, 2020).

Growth Mindset and Positive Attitude: Individuals should be praised for demonstrating a growth attitude, accepting difficulties, and keeping a positive attitude toward learning and personal development. Recognize their confidence in their abilities and readiness to learn from their failures. (Limeri et al., 2020; Rohne, 2015)

Transferable Skills: Emphasize people's capacity to use their knowledge and abilities in real-world settings. Recognize their ability to establish connections between concepts, analyse critically, and apply their knowledge in new settings (Suanthong, 2023; Wang et al., 2021).

Intrinsic Motivation and Passion: Emphasize individuals' capacity to use their knowledge and abilities in real-world settings. Recognize their ability to establish connections between concepts, think critically, and apply what they've learned in new contexts (Suanthong, 2023; Wang et al., 2021).

Finally, offer precise and meaningful compliments that emphasise work, progress, resilience, and the development of a growth mindset. Individuals are more inclined to embrace challenges,

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persevere in their efforts, and continue their journey of learning and progress if these qualities are recognised and reinforced.

7. Potential challenges and limitations of providing effective feedback and praises.

Effective feedback and praises are critical to enabling learning, growth, and mindset development. However, delivering feedback and praises is not without its difficulties and constraints. The educators and policymakers can have potential hurdles and constraints while providing criticism and praise, as well as the implications for mindset development.

One of the most difficult aspects of offering effective feedback is finding a balance between positive reinforcement and constructive criticism. While praise can promote motivation and self-esteem, overly general or exaggerated praise can undercut its effectiveness and impede people's growth and development. Constructive criticism, on the other hand, can be useful for identifying areas for improvement, but it must be presented in a way that retains individuals' motivation and develops a growth mindset.

Another problem is the individual variances in receiving and processing comments and praise. When it comes to feedback, people have different preferences and sensitivities, and what one person finds encouraging and helpful may be discouraging to another. Understanding these individual variances is essential for customizing feedback and praise to match individuals' requirements and effectively promote their mindset growth.

Cultural and environmental factors also make offering criticism and compliments difficult. Different cultural norms and expectations might have an impact on how feedback is provided and received. Furthermore, the setting in which feedback is given, such as educational institutions or workplaces, can influence individuals' views and responses to feedback and praise.

Additionally, the possible limitations of feedback and praises should be addressed. Feedback may not always reach its intended recipients, or it may be misunderstood or rejected. If praise is not real or meaningful, it loses its impact and fails to develop a growth mindset. To ensure that feedback and compliments properly contribute to attitude development, it is critical to address these limits and investigate solutions for overcoming them.

8. Practical recommendations for educators, parents, and policymakers

8.1 Provide Specific and Constructive Feedback: When providing feedback, be explicit about what the individual performed well and places for growth. Avoid broad or ambiguous remarks that do not provide specific direction. Individuals can better grasp how to learn and develop their talents if they receive targeted feedback.

8.2 Emphasize Effort and Process: Instead of focusing exclusively on outcomes or innate abilities, praise individuals' efforts, approaches, and the process they used to attain their goals. Emphasizing the value of hard work, resilience, and effective problem-solving

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fosters a growth mindset by demonstrating that development is possible with devotion and determination.

- 8.3 *Foster a Safe and Supportive Environment:* Create an environment in which people feel secure to take risks and make errors without fear of being judged or failing. Encourage an open discourse in which people may ask questions, seek support, and share their achievements and challenges. This encouraging environment fosters a growth attitude by valuing the learning process and recognizing failures as chances for improvement.
- 8.4 *Encourage Self-Reflection and Goal Setting:* Teach them the value of self-reflection and encourage them to develop realistic and attainable goals. Assist them in identifying their strengths and areas for improvement, as well as in formulating methods to overcome obstacles and achieve their goals. Goals should be reviewed and revised on a regular basis to promote continual growth and development.
- 8.5 *Promote a Growth Mindset Language:* Use language that fosters the belief that Level of intelligence and abilities are changeable. Encourage people to use terms like "I can get better with practise" or "I haven't mastered it yet" instead of fixed mindset statements like "I'm not good at this." Individuals can build a more optimistic and growth-oriented mindset by changing their language.
- 8.6 *Model a Growth Mindset:* It is critical for schools, parents, and policymakers to demonstrate a growth mindset. Prove to develop perseverance, resilience, and desire to learn from failures. Share personal examples of overcoming obstacles and emphasise the necessity of ongoing learning and progress. We inspire others to adopt a growth attitude by serving as role models.
- 8.7 *Provide Opportunities for Growth and Mastery:* Create a curriculum or learning environment that allows individuals to participate in challenging assignments, problem-solving activities, and skill-building activities. Encourage them to try new things, get out of their comfort zones, and enjoy the learning experience. Individuals can strengthen their skills and cultivate a growth attitude by offering these opportunities.
- 8.8 *Offer Timely and Specific Praises:* When praising someone, be precise about the work, methods, or success they've made. Recognize their dedication, improvement, or imaginative problem-solving. Avoid vague praises that do not provide useful feedback. By acknowledging and affirming individuals' efforts and success, timely and particular praises support the growth attitude.
- 8.9 *Collaborate with Parents and Policymakers:* Collaboration among educators, parents, and policymakers is essential for fostering a cohesive and supportive learning environment. Collaborate to create policies and procedures that foster a growth mindset, align feedback and praise systems, and give chances for professional development for instructors. This collaborative approach maintains consistency and has the possible influence on mindset development.
- 8.10 *Continuously Assess and Adapt:* Evaluate the effectiveness of feedback and praising strategies in creating a growth attitude on a regular basis. Collect input from students,

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parents, and educators to assess the impact and make improvements as needed. Keep up to date on research and best practises in mindset development to fine-tune approaches and assure continuous improvement.

Educators, parents, and legislators can foster a growth mindset and assist individuals' learning, motivation, and personal development by applying these practical guidelines. We can inspire individuals to accept difficulties, persevere in the face of failures, and prosper academically and personally by providing targeted feedback, genuine praise, and an emphasis on effort and improvement.

9. Conclusion

This study work has investigated the effects of feedback and praise on mindset development. it looked at the concept of mindset, specifically the differences between fixed and growth mindsets, and how they affect people's learning and performance. It has particularly looked at the role of feedback in mindset development, emphasising its importance in encouraging a growth mindset by emphasising effort, progress, and improvement.

Furthermore, it has highlighted the importance of praises in mindset development, emphasising their ability to build a growth mindset by recognising individuals' resilience, strategies, and positive attitudes. Feedback and praises both play important roles in moulding 's thoughts about their skills as well as their approach to learning and challenges.

It has emphasized the need of offering detailed, timely, and constructive feedback that emphasises effort, progress, and the development of a growth mindset. Similarly, It has emphasised the need of using compliments to encourage a growth mindset by acknowledging people's resilience, creativity, and willingness to take risks.

However, we must recognise the potential difficulties and limitations of offering appropriate feedback and praises. Individuals' various needs and preferences, cultural variables, and the balance between honest feedback and positive reinforcement are few issues that educators, parents, and policymakers may handle.

We offer practical advice for educators, parents, and policymakers in relation to the findings. Fostering a growth mindset culture, offering ongoing and precise feedback, matching feedback and praise with growth mindset principles, encouraging self-reflection and self-awareness, and acknowledging individual development and effort are all examples.

By implementing these recommendations, educators, parents, and policymakers can help individuals develop a growth mindset, promoting a love of learning, resilience, and a belief in the power of effort and improvement.

Finally, the effects of feedback and praise on mindset are significant. We may foster a growth mindset in persons by grasping the principles of fixed mindset and growth mindset, utilising

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the power of appropriate feedback and praises, and recognising potential challenges. As a result, enhanced motivation, resilience, and a lifelong love of learning can result.

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